

Rainfall Measurement

Monitoring the world around us since 1864

MUNRO

R W Munro Limited

Monitoring the World Around us Since 1864

The Founder Robert William Munro, F.R.Met.Soc. 1839-1912

Established in 1864, R W Munro has become synonymous with meteorological and hydrological equipment sales and service. Since production of the first Dines Pressure Tube Anemometer in 1892, R W Munro has achieved a reputation for excellence in providing instruments and systems of the highest quality to measure, monitor and record environmental phenomena. Today, Munro products extend right across the technological spectrum. Combining the traditional reliability of Munro craftsmanship with the benefits of the latest electronics enables Munro to supply standard and specialist equipment to meteorological offices, water authorities and government departments world-wide.

Equipment For The Measurement Of Rainfall

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Rainfall Measuring Equipment

At climatological and synoptic stations worldwide, it is standard procedure to measure rainfall at each scheduled hour, then calculate the total rainfall during the previous six-hour and twelve-hour period.

Regular rainfall measurement is also an essential requirement in many aspects of agriculture, forestry, industry, education and other activities. Rainfall is rarely uniform in intensity or duration across a wide area, so continuous data on local conditions is of particular importance to farmers and those concerned with irrigation, scientists researching into crop performance and soil erosion, and to water and river authorities in respect of reservoir supplies and ground water feeding into rivers. Accurate measurement is also essential for calculating evaporation.

The rain gauge is the standard method of collection. This has to be sited in a location, which is representative of the rainfall area to be measured. Often a network of sites will be integrated to cover average rainfall over a large area. Rainfall at any one place against time is expressed in terms of the depth to which it would cover the surface locally, assuming there was no loss by evaporation or run-off. The rain gauge is often used in conjunction with other instruments for a full picture of local climatic conditions.

Munro offer a range of precision rain gauges to meet all applications, all manufactured to a British Meteorological Office specification, ensuring accurate rainfall collection and measurement.

Daily Rain Gauges

Rain Gauges are located to collect rain over a specified area. The rain falls through a defined aperture and into an inner can. The contents are then measured, normally once a day, by pouring into a measuring jar. Universally used by professional and amateur meteorologists, these models are also ideal for educational, industrial and other applications.

Meteorological Office Mk 2 Splayed-Base Rain Gauge R001

The unit is made from stout copper sheet with soldered seams, and the splayed base provides extra stability. It has a 127mm diameter brass rim and is supplied with an inner can with pouring lip and a handle, an ordinary pattern glass measuring jar and a rainfall record book. A brown half-Winchester glass collecting bottle can be supplied as an alternative to the measuring jar.

Meteorological Office Mk 1A Cylindrical Rain Gauge R003

Construction of this general purpose rain gauge is also in copper sheet, with soldered seams and a 127mm diameter brass rim, but the design is cylindrical. It is supplied with accessories, as for the splayed-base model.

Measuring Jars

These are supplied in three patterns for use with either 127mm or 203mm diameter rain gauges. Each is clearly graduated and has a 10mm capacity.

British Meteorological Office Pattern R007 - R009

The high precision tapered base is for accurate measurement of minute amounts of water.

Ordinary Pattern R011 - R013

A flat bottomed jar with etched figures which is supplied as standard with Munro Rain Gauges.

Camden Pattern R015 - R017

This combines the free standing facility of the ordinary pattern with the high precision of the tapered base type.

SPECIFICATIONS

Reference	R001	R003
Dia. of Aperture	127 mm	127 mm
Area of Aperture	12668 mm ²	12668 mm ²
Rainfall Capacity	140 mm	140 mm
Dimensions	490 mm (H) x 216 mm (D)	480 mm (H) x 140 mm (D)
Weight	2.75 Kg	2.1 Kg
Reference	R007	R009
For use with gauge	127 mm	203 mm
Reference	R011	R013
For use with gauge	127 mm	203 mm
Reference	R015	R017
For use with gauge	127 mm	203 mm

Recording Rain Gauges

The well-proven Dines Tilting Siphon Rain Gauge produces a recording of rainfall against time. The automatic tilting action ensures unlimited collecting capacity. It is frequently used in conjunction with a daily rain gauge to provide a permanent record of the onset and cessation of rainfall, together with variations in intensity. The Tipping Bucket Rain Gauge is suitable for use with telemetry or data-logging equipment and ideal for monitoring in remote locations.

Tilting Siphon Rain Gauge - Temperate Model R200

The movement of a float in the collecting chamber causes a pen to mark a daily or weekly chart, which is viewed through the hinged front window. When 5mm of rain has fallen - represented on the chart by a linear distance of 50mm - the pen is at the top of the chart and the chamber tilts and empties. The pen then returns to the bottom of the chart to start recording again. The Gauge is constructed from non-ferrous materials and supplied with a hand-wound clock. There is a choice of either fibre disposable pen or nickel-silver pen and ink.

Tilting Siphon Rain Gauge - Tropical Model R208

This Rain Gauge is similar to the temperate model, but has a smaller collecting aperture and siphons after 25mm of rainfall, enabling it to be used in areas of intense rainfall. The instrument is finished in white paint and is fitted with a radiation shield to reduce evaporation from the cone.

Tipping Bucket Rain Gauge R100 Series

This Gauge can be used with a data logger, counter or event recorder, so making it ideal for remote monitoring and recording, or network integration. The principle is well-proved and ensures accuracy with unlimited capacity. The bucket is divided into two parts and mounted on a tungsten axle and pivots. When one part fills, the bucket tips to discharge the water to the ground and also activates a pair of switches. The other part of the bucket then fills and the cycle is repeated, as long as rain is falling. A wire mesh filter prevents the ingress of debris or insects. Other features include a levelling adjustment with indicator and the option of heating, to prevent ice forming in the bucket assembly, down to a temperature of -6°C. A deep cover option with the funnel set 127mm below the rim to prevent rain bouncing out during sudden downpours.

SPECIFICATIONS

Reference	R200/R202	R208/R210
Recording period	daily/weekly	daily/weekly
Dia. of aperture	287.3 mm	128.5 mm
Area of aperture	64827 mm ²	12969 mm ²
Rainfall capacity	unlimited	unlimited
Siphoning occurs	every 5 mm	every 25 mm
Siphoning time	6-8 seconds	6-8 seconds
Dimensions	840 (H) x 502 (D) mm	840 (H) x 502 (D) mm
Weight	36.0 kg	33.5 kg
R100 series		
Diameter of aperture	203 mm	Weight (std. cover) 5.8 kg
Area of aperture	32365 mm ²	Weight (deep cover) 7.0 kg
Rainfall capacity	unlimited	Fixing details 3x9.9 mm holes on 260 mm PCD
Dimensions		Heating 12 V dc, 1.45 A
Base dia.	280 mm	17.45 W
Height (std. cover)	310 mm	Calibration (mm per tip) (R102) 0.2
Height (deep cover)	437 mm	(R104) 0.5
		(R106) 0.25

R W Munro Ltd. reserve the right to alter specifications of equipment at any time, in the interests of improving quality and performance

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